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DISPARITY OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN ASSAM: An Inter-district Study

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Abstract:

The development of all the regions of a country is never uniform whether the country is developed or underdeveloped. The infrastructure plays a crucial role for this uneven development. In India, this widespread disparity in infrastructural development is very acute in case of Assam. In the early phases of India's planned economic development efforts were mainly confined to sectoral economic development with greater emphasis on raising the per capita income of the people. As a result, certain areas went ahead leaving others lagging behind and thereby creating disparity among the different states in India. The economy as whole also faced the problems of sectoral imbalance and widening gap between the rich and the poor. In this regard Assam is ranked as one of the poor states in the country. In the present study, a critical analysis has been made in the interdistrict inequality in infrastructure sector in Assam.

1. Introduction:

Infrastructure plays a crucial role in the economic progress of a state or a region. Good and healthy infrastructure raises productivity and lowers production cost. According to World Bank (Songco, 2002), 1 percent increase in the stock of infrastructure is associated with 1 percent growth in GDP across the country. An empirical study by Diechmann et. al. (2002) for Mexico shows that a 10 percent increase in the market access leads to 6 percent labour productivity. The adequacy of infrastructure diversifies production, expand trade and speed up the overall economic progress. It also enhances the quality of life by providing amenities to the people. Infrastructure services e.g. transport, water, electricity, health are immediate inputs to production. Any reduction of these input costs raises the profitability of production which enhances the level of output, income and employment. Infrastructure services also raise the productivity of other

factors of production such as labour, capital etc. This is made possible by permitting the transition from manual to electric, electronic machinery reducing workers' working hours and improving information flows. On all this accounts, it is said that infrastructure is an "unpaid factor of production." Infrastructure in any location creates sound and atmosphere for business investment both by public as well as private sectors.

Infrastructure services like power, transport, health facilities, educational facilities, roads and railways, postal and bank services, telecommunication etc raise productivity as well as quality of life and welfare of the people. One of the major challenges faced by most of the developing region is to provide proper infrastructural services to meet demands of industry, business households and other users.

2. Objectives:

The main objectives of this study are-

- i) To analyze the interdistrict disparity of infrastructure in Assam.
- ii) To find out the status of the districts in terms of infrastructural development.

3. Methodology:

Collection of Data:

The data we have collected for this study are from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data are collected from field survey. But the analysis mainly based on secondary data. The Secondary data we have collected from

- i) Economic Survey of Assam, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Govt. of Assam
- ii) Statistical Hand Book of Assam, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Govt. of Assam
- iii) Agricultural Statistics, Directorate of Agriculture, Govt. of Assam

Coverage:

So far as interdistrict development disparities are concerned our field of study is in the entire state of Assam and the sampling frame consists of the erstwhile 23 districts of Assam. Data on selected indicators of agriculture have been obtained in respect of the 23 districts of Assam.

*Statistical Methods applied in this study:***Indexing Method:**

In this method value of each indicator of infrastructural development worked out for each district by taking the value of indicator for the state as 100. Then converted values of those indicators in respect of each district are added up and this aggregate value is divided by 10, the number of indicators to get average development index (ADI) value for each district. This value for each district is compared with the state average of value of 100 relating to all the ten chosen indicators. If the ADI value of a district is less than 100, then the district is termed as backward (B) and if it is greater than or equal to 100 then it is termed as relatively developed (RD).

Deprivation Method:

The deprivation indicator I_{ij} for the j^{th} district ($j= 1, 2, 3, \dots, 23$) with respect to the i^{th} indicator ($i= 1, 2, 3, \dots, 10$) is given by

$$I_{ij} = \frac{\text{Actual Value} - \text{Minimum Value}}{\text{Maximum Value} - \text{Minimum Value}}$$

The maximum value implies the maximum of the value of the 23 districts in respect of the i^{th} indicator. Actual value means the value of the j^{th} district in respect of the i^{th} indicator and minimum value means the minimum value of the 23 districts in respect of the i^{th} indicator.

4. Indicators of Infrastructural development:

Researchers, those have been studying relating to district level disparities on the basis of some indicators and for construction of composite index of development used the methodology of equal weightage indexing method and deprivation method. In the light of such studies we have chosen 10 indicators depending upon secondary data in the district level in the two periods of time e.g. 2002-03 and 2008-09. The indicators chosen in respect of infrastructure development are-

- i) Literacy rate
- ii) Number of primary schools per 10000 population
- iii) Number of high schools per 10000 population
- iv) Number health centres per lakh population
- v) Number of beds per lakh population
- vi) Percentage of urban population
- vii) Roads per lakh population (in km)
- viii) Roads per 100 sq. km. (in km)
- ix) Percentage of electrified villages to total villages
- x) Number of bank branches per lakh of population

5. The Analysis:

Table 1 shows the ranking of districts of Assam by indexing method and deprivation method with respect to infrastructural development for the year 2002-03. In 2002-03,

Table 1: Ranking of districts of Assam by index method and deprivation method with respect to infrastructural development for the year 2002-03

Name of the District	Index Method			Deprivation Index		
	Average Development Index for Infrastructure	Rank	Status	Economic Development Index for Infrastructure	Rank	Status
Barpeta	84.702	15	B	0.260	16	B
Bongaigaon	85.089	14	B	0.264	15	B
Cachar	81.120	19	B	0.266	14	B
Darrang	85.781	13	B	0.266	13	B
Dhemaji	83.442	16	B	0.219	21	B
Dhubri	72.787	23	B	0.169	23	B
Dibrugarh	102.143	7	RD	0.387	7	B
Goalpara	96.683	10	B	0.355	9	B
Golaghat	101.629	8	RD	0.367	8	B
Hailakandi	78.141	21	B	0.240	20	B
Jorhat	125.887	3	RD	0.520	3	MD
Kamrup	128.620	2	RD	0.533	2	MD
Karbi Anglong	97.505	9	B	0.309	11	B
Karimganj	76.608	22	B	0.250	18	B
Kokrajhar	82.628	18	B	0.210	22	B
Morigaon	80.697	20	B	0.249	19	B
Nagaon	93.963	11	B	0.353	10	B
Nalbari	111.396	5	RD	0.455	5	B
North Cachar Hills	232.114	1	RD	0.783	1	MD
North Lakhimpur	105.911	6	RD	0.394	6	B
Sibsagar	119.340	4	RD	0.513	4	MD
Sonitpur	83.328	17	B	0.260	17	B
Tinsukia	90.485	12	B	0.293	12	B
ASSAM	100.00					

indexing method has classified fifteen districts as backward in infrastructure and eight districts as relatively developed. On the other hand, deprivation method has classified nineteen districts as backward and four districts as moderately developed. The backward districts in infrastructure by indexing method are Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Darrang, Dhemaji, Dhubri, Goalpara, Hailakandi, Karbi Anglong, Karimganj, Kokrajhar, Morigaon, Nagaon, Sonitpur and Tinsukia whereas the relatively developed districts are Dibrugarh, Golaghat, Jorhat, Kamrup, Nalbari, North Cachar Hills, North Lakhimpur, and Sibsagar. According to the deprivation method the backward districts are Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Darrang, Dhemaji, Dhubri, Dibrugarh, Goalpara, Golaghat, Hailakandi, Karbi Anglong, Karimganj, Kokrajhar, Morigaon, Nagaon, Nalbari, North Lakhimpur, Sonitpur and Tinsukia whereas the moderately developed districts are Jorhat, Kamrup, North Cachar Hills and Sibsagar.

In the year 2008-09, the situation is not improved much more improved than the 2002-03, for example, only very few districts e.g. Dibrugarh, Golaghat, Jorhat, Kamrup, Nalbari, North Cachar Hills, North Lakhimpur, and Sibsagar are relatively developed and the rest are backward out of 23 districts. The situation is no more encouraging under deprivation method from our study we find only four districts are moderately developed are Jorhat, Kamrup, North Cachar Hills and Sibsagar. However, these four districts retains in the category of either relatively developed or moderately developed over the period.

One thing is to be noted that a number of relatively developed districts by index method in the year 2008-09 has decreased while the number of backward category districts increased more in both these periods.

Table 2 shows the ranking of districts of Assam by indexing method and deprivation method with respect to infrastructural development for the year 2008-09. In 2008-09, indexing method has classified eighteen districts as backward in infrastructure and six districts as relatively developed. On the other hand, deprivation method has classified twenty one districts as backward and two districts as moderately developed. The backward districts in infrastructure by indexing method in 2008-09 are Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Darrang, Dhemaji, Dhubri, Dibrugarh, Goalpara, Golaghat, Hailakandi, Karbi Anglong, Karimganj, Kokrajhar, Morigaon, Nagaon, Sonitpur and Tinsukia whereas the relatively developed districts are Jorhat, Kamrup, Nalbari, North Cachar Hills, North Lakhimpur, and Sibsagar.

According to the deprivation method the backward districts are Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Darrang, Dhemaji, Dhubri, Dibrugarh, Goalpara, Golaghat, Hailakandi, Jorhat, Karbi Anglong, Karimganj, Kokrajhar, Morigaon, Nagaon, Nalbari, North Lakhimpur, Sibsagar, Sonitpur and Tinsukia whereas the moderately developed districts are Kamrup and North Cachar Hills.

Table 2: Ranking of districts of Assam by index method and deprivation method with respect to infrastructural development for the year 2008-09

Name of the District	Index Method			Deprivation Index		
	Average Development Index for Infrastructure	Rank	Status	Economic Development Index for Infrastructure	Rank	Status
Barpeta	81.083	20	B	0.244	21	B
Bongaigaon	97.922	8	B	0.351	8	B
Cachar	79.111	22	B	0.257	20	B
Darrang	95.603	11	B	0.333	9	B
Dhemaji	94.467	12	B	0.285	16	B
Dhubri	73.982	23	B	0.173	23	B
Dibrugarh	96.833	9	B	0.355	7	B
Goalpara	93.315	14	B	0.296	14	B
Golaghat	93.428	13	B	0.325	12	B
Hailakandi	96.121	10	B	0.327	11	B
Jorhat	119.622	3	RD	0.488	3	B
Kamrup	126.905	2	RD	0.530	2	MD
Karbi Anglong	98.028	7	B	0.330	10	B
Karimganj	81.298	19	B	0.284	17	B
Kokrajhar	88.330	16	B	0.274	19	B
Morigaon	86.692	17	B	0.288	15	B
Nagaon	85.014	18	B	0.281	18	B
Nalbari	114.586	4	RD	0.482	4	B
North Cachar Hills	218.330	1	RD	0.741	1	MD
North Lakhimpur	101.764	6	RD	0.371	6	B
Sibsagar	108.020	5	RD	0.435	5	B
Sonitpur	79.483	21	B	0.232	22	B
Tinsukia	90.059	15	B	0.297	13	B
ASSAM	100.00					

5. Findings:

The major finding of this study is that the moderately developed districts are Kamrup and North Cachar Hills by both the methods but districts like Jorhat, Nalbari, North Lakhimpur and Sibsagar are relatively developed compared to other districts of the state. And the rest of the districts like Barpeta, Bongaigaon, Cachar, Darrang, Dhemaji, Dhubri, Dibrugarh, Goalpara, Golaghat, Hailakandi, Karbi Anglong, Karimganj, Kokrajhar, Morigaon, Nagaon, Sonitpur and Tinsukia are backward by both the methods.

It was found that the number of relatively backward districts in 2002-03 and 2008-09 almost remained same by both the indexing method and deprivation method. From the analysis, it has been found that though development takes place to some extent in the infrastructure sector in Assam there is still remaining the wide disparities in the rank and status of the districts within the state.

6. Conclusion:

Every method of measuring of a parameter has its own merits and limitations. We have used two methods of measuring development disparities among the districts of Assam at district level. These are Indexing method and Deprivation method. While indexing method is relative measure, deprivation method is an absolute measure. Indexing method classifies a region either as relatively developed or backward. In case of district level analysis in Assam if the value of composite development index for a district is higher than or equal to that of state average of Assam, then the district has been categorized as relatively developed and if the value is less than that of Assam, then the district is categorized as backward. This is based on the supposition that in the country's perspective Assam is backward. On the other hand, the term relatively developed cannot give us an idea regarding the degree of development.

Deprivation method is an absolute measure and it throws light on the degree of deprivation and development. However, in order to apply this method one should get the minimum and the maximum values in respect of an indicator especially by a national or international agency. For example, in the connection of Human Development Index (HDI) in Human Development Report published by United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 1990, the minimum and maximum values for the indicator life expectancy of birth have been specified as 25 years and 85 years respectively. In our case, our analysis based on deprivation method would have been more realistic should we have been able to take the minimum and maximum values of each indicator from the list of indicators. For non-availability of such value we have taken the minimum and maximum values for each indicator from the list of values pertaining to the districts of Assam only in respect of the indicator.

We have mainly ranked the disparities in the levels of overall development in Assam at district level, on the basis of secondary as well as primary data. We have not analyzed the causes behind such disparities. Again, we have not found a single developed district as the score for developed status is 0.8 or more is not found in any of the case by deprivation method. The discovery of the cases behind large variations among the districts in Assam, in respect of some developmental indicators may be a subject matter for research in future. Such research investigation may be carried out on the basis of an investigation.

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APPENDIX

Table 1: Districtwise percentage of Literacy in Assam

Sl No.	Name of the District	Literacy Rate (in percentage)			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	43.24	20	56.24	19
2	Bongaigaon	49.06	15	59.33	15
3	Cachar	59.16	4	67.82	7
4	Darrang	42.00	21	55.44	20
5	Dhemaji	53.84	12	64.48	11
6	Dhubri	38.36	23	48.21	22
7	Dibrugarh	58.32	7	68.96	5
8	Goalpara	46.81	18	48.03	23
9	Golaghat	58.54	6	69.38	4
10	Hailakandi	53.07	13	59.64	14
11	Jorhat	65.51	1	76.33	1
12	Kamrup	65.04	2	74.16	3
13	Karbi Anglong	45.57	19	57.70	18
14	Karimganj	54.71	11	66.24	10
15	Kokrajhar	40.47	22	51.63	21
16	Morigaon	47.99	17	58.53	17
17	Nagaon	54.74	10	61.73	12
18	Nalbari	55.99	9	67.23	9
19	North Cachar Hills	57.76	8	67.62	8
20	North Lakhimpur	58.96	5	68.56	6
21	Sibsagar	64.46	3	74.47	2
22	Sonitpur	48.14	16	59.00	16
23	Tinsukia	50.28	14	60.95	13
	Assam	52.70		62.68	

Sources:

(i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues

(ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues

Table 2: Districtwise number of Primary schools per 10000 populations in Assam

Sl No.	Name of the District	Number of Primary Schools per 10000 population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	12.60	9	13.1	11
2	Bongaigaon	10.60	14	15.6	8
3	Cachar	11.20	13	11.7	14
4	Darrang	10.50	15	19	3
5	Dhemaji	12.90	8	14.8	10
6	Dhubri	9.10	19	9.5	19
7	Dibrugarh	9.14	18	10	18
8	Goalpara	12.00	12	11.4	15
9	Golaghat	9.40	17	10.6	16
10	Hailakandi	18.20	2	18.5	4
11	Jorhat	14.40	5	15.7	7
12	Kamrup	8.90	20	9.2	20
13	Karbi Anglong	14.30	6	17.3	5
14	Karimganj	12.60	10	12.4	13
15	Kokrajhar	12.20	11	12.8	12
16	Morigaon	9.50	16	10.5	17
17	Nagaon	8.60	21	8.7	21
18	Nalbari	14.00	7	21.1	2
19	North Cachar Hills	35.40	1	38	1
20	North Lakhimpur	14.50	4	15.4	9
21	Sibsagar	16.10	3	16.3	6
22	Sonitpur	7.70	22	8	22
23	Tinsukia	6.40	23	7.3	23
	Assam	12.62		14.21	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Directorate of Elementary Education, Assam

Table 3: Districtwise number of High schools per 10000 populations in Assam

SI No.	Name of the District	Number of High Schools per 10000 population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	1.72	10	1.76	2
2	Bongaigaon	1.26	15	2.07	18
3	Cachar	1.01	18	1.51	5
4	Darrang	1.46	13	1.54	7
5	Dhemaji	2.55	3	3.9	17
6	Dhubri	0.91	19	1.21	1
7	Dibrugarh	1.19	17	1.32	21
8	Goalpara	1.79	8	1.85	10
9	Golaghat	1.69	11	1.83	6
10	Hailakandi	0.72	23	4.53	15
11	Jorhat	2.49	4	2.53	16
12	Kamrup	1.81	7	2.14	20
13	Karbi Anglong	1.99	6	2.42	22
14	Karimganj	0.82	21	0.91	12
15	Kokrajhar	0.77	22	1.46	19
16	Morigaon	1.61	12	1.78	8
17	Nagaon	1.30	14	1.31	23
18	Nalbari	2.23	5	2.59	3
19	North Cachar Hills	3.60	1	4.57	14
20	North Lakhimpur	2.83	2	3.76	9
21	Sibsagar	1.74	9	1.82	11
22	Sonitpur	1.25	16	1.42	13
23	Tinsukia	0.91	20	1.62	4
	Assam	1.64		2.17	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Directorate of Secondary Education, Assam

Table 4: Districtwise number of Health centres per lakh populations

SI No.	Name of the District	No. of health centres per lakh of population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	3.41	16	3.17	19
2	Bongaigaon	5.30	6	4.85	10
3	Cachar	2.22	22	2.36	23
4	Darrang	3.79	14	2.86	21
5	Dhemaji	2.99	18	4.57	12
6	Dhubri	2.81	19	3.30	18
7	Dibrugarh	4.69	9	3.41	17
8	Goalpara	4.01	12	5.72	5
9	Golaghat	6.56	4	5.29	8
10	Hailakandi	2.21	23	2.95	20
11	Jorhat	5.05	7	5.55	6
12	Kamrup	4.46	10	5.09	9
13	Karbi Anglong	6.65	3	7.63	3
14	Karimganj	2.29	21	4.78	11
15	Kokrajhar	6.77	2	8.60	1
16	Morigaon	4.00	13	5.41	7
17	Nagaon	3.71	15	3.76	14
18	Nalbari	5.89	5	5.80	4
19	North Cachar Hills	9.13	1	8.06	2
20	North Lakhimpur	4.05	11	4.27	13
21	Sibsagar	5.03	8	3.51	16
22	Sonitpur	3.28	17	3.70	15
23	Tinsukia	2.35	20	2.52	22
	Assam	4.38		4.66	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Directorate of Health, Assam

Table 5: Districtwise number of Medical Beds per lakh populations

Sl No.	Name of the District	Number of beds per lakh population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	18.75	17	27.56	16
2	Bongaigaon	13.24	23	26.08	17
3	Cachar	16.47	19	17.99	22
4	Darrang	28.13	10	31.51	12
5	Dhemaji	21.25	15	31.47	13
6	Dhubri	23.71	14	29.50	14
7	Dibrugarh	18.63	18	20.42	21
8	Goalpara	23.86	13	42.58	6
9	Golaghat	32.56	8	34.66	10
10	Hailakandi	14.73	21	38.31	8
11	Jorhat	39.15	3	42.83	5
12	Kamrup	36.18	5	36.55	9
13	Karbi Anglong	37.25	4	49.92	3
14	Karimganj	16.44	20	22.02	20
15	Kokrajhar	30.25	9	32.24	11
16	Morigaon	20.62	16	24.48	19
17	Nagaon	24.65	12	25.49	18
18	Nalbari	45.16	2	47.18	4
19	North Cachar Hills	98.65	1	101.02	1
20	North Lakhimpur	35.53	6	49.94	2
21	Sibsagar	34.95	7	38.41	7
22	Sonitpur	13.95	22	14.27	23
23	Tinsukia	25.30	11	27.65	15
	Assam	29.11		35.31	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Directorate of Health, Assam

Table 6: Districtwise roads in km per lakh population in the two periods 2002-03 and 2008-09

Sl No.	Name of the District	Road in km per lakh of population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	89.75	18	87.00	18
2	Bongaigaon	95.36	16	98.40	16
3	Cachar	65.11	21	68.10	21
4	Darrang	106.19	12	127.40	10
5	Dhemaji	154.53	5	217.50	2
6	Dhubri	59.25	22	62.30	22
7	Dibrugarh	124.31	8	132.20	7
8	Goalpara	102.39	13	112.40	12
9	Golaghat	160.71	4	172.60	5
10	Hailakandi	69.48	19	72.20	20
11	Jorhat	164.09	3	175.90	4
12	Kamrup	96.06	15	100.40	15
13	Karbi Anglong	45.69	23	53.90	23
14	Karimganj	67.15	20	85.20	19
15	Kokrajhar	106.62	11	111.10	13
16	Morigaon	99.89	14	131.80	8
17	Nagaon	107.41	10	103.10	14
18	Nalbari	121.51	9	131.40	9
19	North Cachar Hills	857.19	1	961.30	1
20	North Lakhimpur	128.86	7	117.30	11
21	Sibsagar	168.88	2	177.80	3
22	Sonitpur	144.35	6	142.30	6
23	Tinsukia	93.64	17	95.60	17
	Assam	140.37		153.79	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Department of PWD, Assam

Table 7: Districtwise distribution of Roads per 100 sq. km in Assam

Sl No.	Name of the District	Roads in km per 100 sq. km area			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	39.70	15	45.70	14
2	Bongaigaon	34.50	18	60.00	7
3	Cachar	24.80	23	25.90	23
4	Darrang	45.90	7	70.70	2
5	Dhemaji	27.20	22	38.40	18
6	Dhubri	40.00	14	45.50	15
7	Dibrugarh	42.50	12	46.30	12
8	Goalpara	56.00	5	50.70	9
9	Golaghat	43.40	11	46.60	11
10	Hailakandi	33.00	19	29.50	21
11	Jorhat	58.00	4	61.70	5
12	Kamrup	55.60	6	58.90	8
13	Karbi Anglong	35.50	16	41.40	17
14	Karimganj	42.40	13	47.50	10
15	Kokrajhar	31.70	21	29.60	20
16	Morigaon	45.00	10	66.00	4
17	Nagaon	60.80	3	60.10	6
18	Nalbari	61.30	2	91.20	1
19	North Cachar Hills	32.70	20	37.00	19
20	North Lakhimpur	45.90	8	45.80	13
21	Sibsagar	67.20	1	70.10	3
22	Sonitpur	45.60	9	44.60	16
23	Tinsukia	35.50	17	29.00	22
	Assam	43.66		49.66	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Department of PWD, Assam

Table 8: Districtwise Percentage of urban population in Assam

Sl No.	Name of the District	Percentage of urban population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	7.62	16	7.70	16
2	Bongaigaon	12.17	7	12.13	8
3	Cachar	13.97	6	13.94	6
4	Darrang	4.91	21	4.97	21
5	Dhemaji	6.91	19	6.79	20
6	Dhubri	11.66	9	12.56	7
7	Dibrugarh	18.77	4	19.28	4
8	Goalpara	8.18	15	8.14	14
9	Golaghat	8.37	14	8.57	13
10	Hailakandi	8.39	13	8.12	15
11	Jorhat	16.91	5	17.15	5
12	Kamrup	35.81	1	36.01	1
13	Karbi Anglong	11.42	10	11.30	10
14	Karimganj	7.33	17	7.33	17
15	Kokrajhar	6.84	20	7.06	19
16	Morigaon	4.91	22	4.89	22
17	Nagaon	12.00	8	12.02	9
18	Nalbari	2.41	23	2.39	23
19	North Cachar Hills	31.19	2	31.60	2
20	North Lakhimpur	7.32	18	7.33	18
21	Sibsagar	9.22	11	9.24	12
22	Sonitpur	8.81	12	10.45	11
23	Tinsukia	19.49	3	19.47	3
	Assam	11.94		12.11	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues

Table 9: Districtwise Percentage of Electrified Villages to Total Villages

SI No.	Name of the District	Percentage of electrified villages to total villages			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	72.26	8	75.14	7
2	Bongaigaon	54.21	16	56.87	16
3	Cachar	70.23	10	73.43	10
4	Darrang	78.29	4	82.36	4
5	Dhemaji	22.78	21	23.79	21
6	Dhubri	59.62	14	62.01	13
7	Dibrugarh	75.24	5	78.84	6
8	Goalpara	82.38	1	85.68	3
9	Golaghat	45.86	19	47.75	19
10	Hailakandi	71.77	9	74.01	8
11	Jorhat	58.88	15	59.97	15
12	Kamrup	68.47	11	69.08	12
13	Karbi Anglong	14.25	23	16.52	23
14	Karimganj	59.91	12	72.13	11
15	Kokrajhar	49.58	18	50.47	18
16	Morigaon	53.38	17	54.22	17
17	Nagaon	72.89	6	73.75	9
18	Nalbari	80.12	3	81.83	5
19	North Cachar Hills	18.97	22	20.50	22
20	North Lakhimpur	43.39	20	44.16	20
21	Sibsagar	82.29	2	87.88	2
22	Sonitpur	59.78	13	61.43	14
23	Tinsukia	72.62	7	88.89	1
	Assam	59.44		62.64	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (iii) Assam State Electricity Board (ASEB)

Table 10: Districtwise number Commercial Banks per lakh populations

SI No.	Name of the District	No. of bank branches per lakh of population			
		Year: 2002-03	Rank	Year: 2008-09	Rank
1	Barpeta	3.60	17	3.83	19
2	Bongaigaon	4.19	14	6.92	5
3	Cachar	4.78	10	5.54	10
4	Darrang	3.20	20	6.31	7
5	Dhemaji	2.99	21	3.18	22
6	Dhubri	2.32	23	2.81	23
7	Dibrugarh	5.80	6	7.26	3
8	Goalpara	4.26	13	3.77	20
9	Golaghat	4.86	9	5.50	11
10	Hailakandi	3.50	18	3.50	21
11	Jorhat	5.95	5	7.21	4
12	Kamrup	6.72	2	10.08	1
13	Karbi Anglong	6.52	3	6.15	8
14	Karimganj	4.48	12	4.76	17
15	Kokrajhar	2.69	22	5.34	12
16	Morigaon	3.48	19	4.77	16
17	Nagaon	3.71	16	3.97	18
18	Nalbari	4.13	15	5.13	14
19	North Cachar Hills	8.59	1	7.98	2
20	North Lakhimpur	5.28	7	5.17	13
21	Sibsagar	5.22	8	5.80	9
22	Sonitpur	4.65	11	5.09	15
23	Tinsukia	6.00	4	6.70	6
	Assam	4.65		5.51	

Sources:

- (i) Statistical Hand Book, Govt. of Assam relevant issues
- (ii) Economic Survey Assam, Govt. of Assam relevant issues